

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF URDU VERSIONS OF VISUAL ANALOGUE SCALE FOR PAIN AND DISABILITY AMONG PATIENTS WITH NON-SPECIFIC NECK PAIN

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Abstract

Purpose: To linguistically translate the Visual Analogue Scale for pain and Visual Analogue Scale for disability into the Urdu language and to test its psychometric properties in patients with nonspecific neck pain among the Urdu-speaking population of Pakistan.

Materials and Methods: Translation of English version of VAS-P and VAS-D were carried out following international guidelines. The VAS was evaluated for reliability, content validity, and construct validity. Baseline assessments included self-structured questionnaire, VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U, NPDS-U, and NPQ-U.

Result: The Urdu versions of VAS-Pain and VAS-Disability exhibited excellent reliability, with ICC values of 0.99 and 0.98, respectively (95% CI). While no ceiling effect was found in either scale, a notable floor effect of 88.2% was observed for VAS-Disability. Both tools showed moderate to weak correlations with NPQ total scores (VAS-Pain: 0.64; VAS-Disability: 0.39) and NPDS total scores (VAS-Pain: 0.45; VAS-Disability: 0.36). Furthermore, significant score differences between patients and healthy individuals supported strong discriminant validity ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: VAS-P and VAS-D were successfully adapted into Urdu and demonstrated good reliability and validity, making it a suitable tool for assessing outcomes in individuals with non-specific neck pain and disability.

INTRODUCTION

The neck region plays a vital role in facilitating head movement and maintaining upright posture, making it highly susceptible to discomfort and mobility issues when affected.(1) Even minor dysfunction in this region can lead to noticeable pain and reduced functional capacity.(2)

Non-specific neck pain (NNP) refers to discomfort located at the back of the neck, between the superior nuchal line and the spinous process of the first thoracic vertebra, without an identifiable anatomical or pathological cause. (3) It has become increasingly common, especially in urbanized and industrial settings.(4) Due to its

complex and multifactorial nature, including biological, psychological, and occupational influences, diagnosing and managing NNP remains challenging. (5) It tends to affect women more frequently and is most prevalent in middle-aged individuals. (5) Many patients experience ongoing or recurring symptoms, and studies show that around 10% develop notable functional limitations, with 5% suffering from significant disability. (3) Prevalence figures vary widely, with lifetime estimates between 14.2% and 71%, and annual reports indicating that up to 50% of adults experience neck pain. (6)

Given the broad impact of NNP on individuals' physical function and quality of life, healthcare providers rely on reliable and valid patient-reported outcome measures. These tools are essential for accurately evaluating pain intensity and disability levels, thereby enabling better clinical decision-making and treatment planning. (7) A variety of validated tools are available to assess the effectiveness of neck pain treatments. (8) VAS is a widely used tool for measuring pain in both research and clinical settings. (9)

VAS pain is a unidimensional scale used to measure pain intensity. (10) It has been commonly used in a variety of adult populations, including those with rheumatic diseases. (11)

VAS is a 100 mm horizontal line on which a patient's pain intensity is represented between "no pain at all" and "worst pain imaginable." And the patient is requested to draw a line at a point that best describes his or her pain level. It is the best tool for describing pain intensity because it's simple, reliable, valid, and gives accurate measurements. (12)

Pain and disability are closely interconnected. VAS for disability follows a similar design to the VAS for pain. It is usually presented as a 100 mm horizontal line on which the patient disability level is represented by a point between the extremes of "no disability" to "very severe disability." (13) According to literature, the original English version of the scale has been translated into these languages: Thai (14), Finnish (15), Turkish (16) and Nigerian (17).

VAS-P and VAS-D has not officially been translated and validated for use in Urdu Language. The aim of the study is to translate VAS-P and VAS-D into Urdu to ensure their accessibility and usability for the for the majority of the population who speak Urdu, addressing the need for culturally appropriate, quick, and reliable pain measurement tools in healthcare.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study involved translation, cultural adaptation and psychometric testing of VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U.

Translation and cross-cultural adaptation

The translation and cross-cultural adaptation process was conducted in accordance with Beaton et al.'s standardized guidelines. (18)

In the first stage, two bilingual native Urdu speakers independently translated the original VAS-P and VAS-D questionnaires from English into Urdu. One translator was informed about the study and the purpose of the scales, while the other lacked medical background and was unaware of the concepts being assessed.

In the second stage, the translators and researchers compared both forward translations and synthesized them into a single common version (T-12), resolving discrepancies through discussion and documentation.

The third stage involved back-translation of the T-12 version into English by two translators whose first language was English. Both were fluent in Urdu and blinded to the original questionnaires and medical concepts.

During the fourth stage, an expert panel, comprising methodologists, health professionals, language experts, and translators, reviewed all translations and developed a pre-final Urdu version. The committee ensured semantic and conceptual equivalence between the source and target versions.

In the final stage, face validity testing was performed on a group of 40 patients using the pre-final VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U versions. Participants completed the questionnaires and were then interviewed to assess clarity, relevance,

and ease of understanding. Feedback confirmed that the questionnaires were well comprehended, and no modifications were required, leading to the final versions for psychometric evaluation.

Following the outcomes of the adaptation process, the VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U versions were finalized and prepared for subsequent psychometric evaluation.

INSTRUMENTS:

Visual Analogue Scale-Pain (VAS-P):

VAS-P is a tool used for pain assessment. It comprises a 100-mm horizontal line anchored by “no pain at all” and “worst pain imaginable.” Patients indicate their current pain level by marking a point on the line. VAS-P is widely recognized for its high reliability and validity in measuring pain intensity. (19)

Visual Analogue Scale-Disability (VAS-D):

VAS-D evaluates the level of functional limitation using a 100-mm line, ranging from “no restriction” to “worst possible restriction.” Patients place a mark corresponding to their perceived level of disability. It is considered a moderately valid and reliable measure for disability assessment. (13)

Neck Pain and Disability Scale-Urdu Version (NPDS-U):

NPDS-U consists of 20 items, each rated on a 100-mm visual analogue scale from 0 (no disability) to 5 (severe disability). The total score is computed on a scale of 0 to 100. It is a widely accepted, valid, and responsive instrument for assessing neck pain and disability in Urdu-speaking patients with nonspecific neck pain (NSNP). (20)

Northwick Park Neck Pain Questionnaire-Urdu Version (NPQ-U):

NPQ-U comprises nine questions with five response options each, covering aspects such as pain intensity, numbness, symptom duration, and impact on daily activities (e.g., carrying, sleeping, working). Scores range from 0 to 36 and are converted into percentages, with higher scores indicating greater disability. NPQ-U is simple to administer, easy to score, and demonstrates

strong psychometric properties in Urdu-speaking populations with NSNP. (21)

Participants:

Patients experiencing non-specific neck pain were recruited from hospitals and clinical settings in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, Pakistan, using a non-probability convenience sampling method. The study, spanning 10 months, commenced after receiving approval from the ethical review committee of Margalla Institute of Health sciences, Rawalpindi. A total of 200 patients meeting the pre-defined inclusion criteria were included: individuals with neck pain, aged 18 to 35 years and both male and females who were able to read Urdu. Additionally, 50 healthy participants with no neck pain or pathology were also recruited. Exclusion criteria included patients with any history of spine surgery, neurological deficits, tumor, rheumatologic diseases, infection or psychiatric disorders.

Procedure:

After obtaining written informed consent, all participants were instructed to complete a battery of questionnaires. Demographic data from both patients and healthy controls were collected using a self-designed form, followed by administration of the VAS-P, VAS-D, NPDS-U, and NPQ-U. Additionally, a subset of 46 patients was randomly selected to retake the VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U questionnaires after a 48-hour interval.

STATISTICAL ANALYSES:

All statistical analyses were conducted using the Statistical Product and Service Solution version 24 software. Continuous variables were shown by mean and standard deviation and the categories were demonstrated in frequency and percentage.

Evaluation of psychometric properties:

The reliability of the VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U was assessed through test-retest reliability and internal consistency. Test-retest reliability was evaluated by administering the scales to a subgroup of 46 patients on two separate occasions, 48 hours apart, to reduce the possibility of recall bias and to ensure clinical stability. Internal consistency

and reproducibility were analyzed using Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC). A ICC value above 0.70 was considered acceptable, indicating excellent reliability. (22)

Content validity was determined by analyzing the completeness of responses, score distribution, and the presence of floor or ceiling effects. Floor or ceiling effects were noted when more than 15% of participants scored the minimum or maximum value on the scale, respectively. (23)

Construct validity was tested through both convergent and discriminant validity. For convergent validity, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between VAS-P-U/VAS-D-U and related instruments, including NPDS-U and NPQ-U. Discriminant validity was established by comparing VAS scores between patients and healthy individuals using independent *t*-tests. (24) The strength of correlations was interpreted as: negligible (0.00–0.10), weak (0.11–0.39), moderate (0.40–0.69), strong (0.70–0.89), and very strong (0.90–1.00).

RESULT:

The translation and cross-cultural adaptation adhered to the guidelines outlined by Beaton et al., involving rigorous forward and backward translations to ensure conceptual and linguistic equivalence. For psychometric evaluation, 200 patients were initially approached; however, 13 did not fulfill the inclusion criteria as they presented with conditions falling under the exclusion criteria, such as infections, prior spine surgery, neurological deficits, tumors, rheumatologic diseases, or psychiatric disorders, resulting in the recruitment of 187 participants for the study. Figure 1 illustrates the patient flow during the validation process. A higher

proportion of females was observed in both the patient and healthy control groups. Demographic data for all participants, including means and standard deviations, are summarized in Table 1.

Reliability:

The reliability assessment of VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U was completed twice within a 48-hour interval with an ICC value of 0.98 for VAS-disability and 0.99 for VAS-pain (95% confidence interval). The values of mean, standard deviation and ICC for all items on VAS-pain and VAS-disability are shown in Table 2.

Content validity:

The floor and ceiling analysis were performed on the total score of the VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U and no floor or ceiling effects were present in VAS-P-U. Similarly, no ceiling effect was found in VAS-D-U. However, an 88.2% floor effect was found in VAS-D-U.

Construct validity:

The correlations between VAS-P-U, VAS-D-U, NPQ and NPDS are shown in table 3. VAS-P-U showed a moderate correlation with NPQ-U total (0.64) and NPDS-U total (0.45), while VAS-D-U correlated weak with NPQ-U total (0.39) and NPDS-U total (0.36). The highest correlation was observed between VAS-P-U and NPDS-U item 2 (0.50) compared to other items.

Construct validity (discriminant validity) was also assessed by determining differences in the total scores of VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U between patients and healthy controls. A significant difference in total scores was found between patients and healthy controls with a *p*-value < 0.001.

Figure 1. Flowchart presenting study group formation

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of patients (N=187).

VARIABLE		PATIENT GROUP MEAN ± S.D. N/% (N=187)	HEALTHY PARTICIPANTS MEAN ± S.D. N/% (N=50)
AGE (YEARS)		26.60±5.18	24.30±4.18
GENDER	Male	75/40.1	12/24.0
	Female	112/59.9	38/76.0
BMI		21.30±3.43	21.56±3.11
PAIN DURATION (MONTHS)		8.27±10.67	N/A
WORK STATUS	Employed	86/46.0	18/36.0
	Unemployed	101/54.0	32/64.0
EDUCATION	Primary	25/13.4	1/2.0
	Secondary	19/10.2	8/16.0
	Undergraduate	80/42.8	34/68.0
	Graduate	63/33.7	7/14.0
VAS	Pain	3.80±1.48	0
	Disability	0.18±0.59	0

Table 1. Mean, standard deviation and ICC (VAS-pain and VAS-disability)

	1 ST MEASUREMENT MEAN±S.D	2 ND MEASUREMENT MEAN±S.D	ICC VALUE	CONFIDENCE INTERVAL (95%)
VAS pain	4.15±1.57	4.15±1.56	0.99	0.96-0.99
VAS Disability	0.26±0.61	0.24±0.52	0.98	0.97-0.99

Table 2. Construct validity (Pearson correlation coefficients) between VAS pain, VAS Disability, NPQ, and NPDS

	VAS pain	VAS disability
NPQ total	0.64	0.39
NPDS total	0.45	0.36

DISCUSSION:

The primary objective of this study was to translate and culturally adapt the VAS-Pain and VAS-Disability into the Urdu language, ensuring they are linguistically and culturally appropriate for patients with non-specific neck pain. Additionally, the study aimed to evaluate the psychometric properties, reliability, and validity, of these Urdu versions. The translation and adaptation process followed the guidelines outlined by Beaton et al. (18)

Our sample size included 200 participants with non-specific neck pain and 50 healthy participants. The mean age in our study was 26.60±5.18 for patients and 24.30±4.18 for healthy participants. This is similar to the Turkish study (VAS-FA) (16), which reported a mean age of 28.71±8.66 for patients and 28.45±8.90 for healthy participants, though it varies from those in other studies including the Nigerian study (56.10±10.10), Finnish study (55.60±16.10) and Thai study (27.60±3.20). (14, 15, 17) The study population had a female majority (59.90%), consistent with other studies, including the Turkish study (55.39% women) and Finnish study (54.50% women) (15, 16), Thai study (73.30% women) and Nigerian study (82.10% women). (17, 25)

Participants found VAS questionnaires easy to understand and complete without additional instructions, similar to the results observed in Turkish and Nigerian adaptations.(16, 17) This confirms the cultural relevance and clarity of the adapted tools. No modifications were necessary during the adaptation process, resulting in a high percentage of completed responses and no missing

data. No ceiling effects were observed for either VAS-P-U or VAS-D-U. This finding indicates that the tool effectively captures low levels of disability and aligns with the absence of floor and ceiling effects observed in Turkish and Finnish studies. (15, 16) Other validation studies did not analyze these effects.(17, 25) Although an 88.2% floor effect was identified in VAS-D-U. It likely reflects the low severity of disability in the participants, as most reported minimal functional impairment. VAS-D-U may not effectively capture minor or mild functional challenges in this age group (18-35 years), leading to a clustering of responses at the lower end of the scale.

The reliability of VAS-P-U and VAS-D-U was assessed in 46 patients, and the results were excellent. The reliability assessment involved test-retest reliability, with an ICC value of 0.99 for VAS pain and 0.98 for VAS disability. These results are consistent with previous studies, such as the Turkish study (0.92-0.95) and the Finnish study (0.97). (15, 16)

Construct validity for the Urdu versions of VAS-P was moderate and VAS-D was weak, with correlations of 0.64 between VAS-P-U and NPQ total, and 0.45 with NPDS total. These moderate correlations are consistent with previous studies, such as the Turkish study (0.47) where similar scales were used. (16) Compared to the Thai study,(25) which showed stronger correlations (0.70 for VAS-FA and FAOS), and the Nigerian study,(17) which focused on translation equivalence (0.98 for Hausa), the moderate and weak correlations in our study may be due to the simple and unidimensional nature of the VAS scales, which focus primarily on specific

constructs like pain intensity and disability levels. The VAS-D, in particular, may not effectively capture subtle or complex aspects of functional impairment, leading to a weaker correlation. Additionally, the low severity of symptoms and minimal functional limitations reported by the relatively young study population likely contributed to a narrow range of responses. As compared to other studies, where the age groups and severity of symptoms varied, this difference in population characteristics could explain the weaker correlation observed in our study.

LIMITATION:

Despite the structured methodology and adherence to standardized protocols, certain limitations were evident in this study. Since VAS-Pain and VAS-Disability are single-item instruments, factor analysis was not applicable. Additionally, internal consistency could not be evaluated, as it pertains to multi-item scales assessing inter-item reliability. Another limitation was the absence of responsiveness analysis, which could have further enhanced the interpretability of the tool's performance over time.

STRENGTHS:

This study offers several key strengths that enhance its significance and credibility. Most notably, it represents the first effort to translate the VAS-Pain and VAS-Disability scales into the Urdu language. The translation and cross-cultural adaptation process followed internationally recognized guidelines, ensuring both linguistic precision and cultural appropriateness. Methodological rigor was maintained throughout the study, with careful attention to ethical, linguistic, and contextual factors, thereby supporting the reliability and validity of the adapted tools.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the VAS-P and VAS-D was successfully adapted into the Urdu language and demonstrated good reliability and validity. Hence, we believe that VAS is acceptable for evaluating outcomes in patients with non-specific neck pain and disability.

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Disclosure statement

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